

Built-in Damage Diagnostics for Composite Structures

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a concept of a diagnostic system using built-in sensors and actuators for detecting damage and monitoring the integrity of in-service composite structures. The proposed system consists of two major diagnostic processes: passive sensing diagnosis (PSD) and active sensing diagnosis (ASD). The PSD utilizes the sensor measurements to determine the change in the structural environments and/or conditions. The ASD generates diagnostic signals from the actuators to diagnose the change in structural integrity resulting from the change in the structural environments and/or conditions.

The concept will be demonstrated in this paper through the detection of impact damage in composites with built-in piezoelectrics. In PSD, a diagnostic method has been developed for identifying impact force and location using distributed sensor measurements for beams and plates.

For active sensing diagnosis (ASD), diagnostic methods based on standing waves and propagating waves are being pursued. A frequency-domain method based on standing waves was developed but its effectiveness was limited to a large damage size and a fixed boundary. Current work is focused on developing diagnostic methods based on the propagating diagnostic waves. A key development for this work is to construct appropriate diagnostic waves for effectively detecting impact damage.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to recent advances in sensor technology, a new concept of damage diagnostics for monitoring the structural integrity of in-service structures has been proposed [1-5]. Because these sensors could be built into composites as an integral part of the structures during manufacture, the built-in damage diagnostics become especially attractive for composite structures design. Optical fibers; micro-machined sensors, and piezoelectrics are being considered as potential candidates for this application.

However, there are major difficulties associated with mechanics, materials, and processing in developing the techniques, besides sensor development. Because a sensor could only measure a parameter at a given location such as a strain or displacement, it is very difficult to practically interpret the local measurements in terms of the overall damage state and the integrity of a structure.

Accordingly, any built-in diagnostic systems that rely solely upon the sensor measure-

ments resulting from the passive activities of the structure would have a limited capability of detecting damage and monitoring the structural integrity. This type of diagnostics will be referred to as passive sensing diagnosis. By introducing actuators in the structure to interact with the sensors, the system becomes active. Actuators could be used to generate needed information for the sensors to further examine the integrity of the structure. Using the actuators to generate diagnostic signals makes the diagnosis active. This type of diagnosis will be referred to as active sensing diagnosis.

An essential component of the active sensing diagnosis is to generate appropriate diagnostic signals for enhancing the detectability of the damage that is of particular concern. This paper will discuss some progress that has been made by the author and his associates [6-9] for the development of the built-in diagnosis for composite structures.

This presentation will primarily focus on the detection of impact damage in composite structures with built-in piezoelectrics as shown in Figure 1. Accordingly, the proposed impact diagnostic system is divided into two processes: passive sensing diagnosis and active sensing diagnosis.

II. PASSIVE SENSING DIAGNOSIS

For given distributed sensor measurements, the PSD process is intended to determine the change in the structural environments or conditions such as changes in temperature, pressure, loading condition, boundary condition, etc. This process would be a nonlinear inverse structural mechanics problem.

Choi and Chang [6] proposed a diagnostic method based on passive sensor measurements for identifying the impact force (energy) and the impact location in beams. The diagnostic method consists of a structural model and a response comparator. The structural model calculates the sensor measurements for a given impact force and location. The comparator compares the sensor measurements with the simulations generated from the structural model to estimate the impact energy and location. Apparently, the prediction of the diagnostic method is limited by the accuracy of the structural model.

Figure 2 shows the reconstructed impact force history from the model based on four simulated sensor outputs corrupted by random white noise as shown in Figure 3. In the figure, x_e is the predicted impact location, and x_o is the actual location. Currently, this diagnostic method is being extended to plates.

III. ACTIVE SENSING DIAGNOSIS

Once the change in the environments is identified such as the impact force, the system would activate the actuators to start the active sensing diagnostic process for detecting internal damage resulting from the change in the environment. There are in general two approaches to excite the structures: standing waves and propagating waves. The standing waves approach is to evaluate the change of frequencies and phase shifts to determine the extent of the damage.

Standing Waves Approach

Keilers and Chang [7-9] proposed a frequency-domain method for detecting delamination in composites using built-in piezoelectrics to generate standing waves. Besides having a structural model and a damage comparator, the method also includes a damage selector, which appropriately chooses the sequence of damage parameters for comparison. Figure 4 shows that the predicted delamination sizes based on the model agreed reasonably well with the actual sizes in composite beams [9].

However, because the frequency response of structures is very sensitive to the change in boundary conditions, the model should be applied to a known and fixed boundary condition. In addition, the frequency response becomes noticeably sensitive to damage only when the size of damage is relatively more than 10 percent of the overall size of the structure [9], which significantly limits this approach from being applied to large structural components.

Propagating Waves Approach

A key development of this approach is to construct appropriate diagnostic signals which could strongly interact with the local damage that is of particular concern and could be well received by neighboring sensors at a minimal distance from the actuator. However, the selection of the diagnostic waves strongly depends upon the type and size of damage, the geometry and material of the structure, as well as the sensor size and location. Accordingly, a knowledge of wave propagations in damaged composites is critically important for this approach.

Figure 5 shows a comparison of sensor measurements responding to a pulse wave generated by piezoelectrics for a composite plate before and after an impact which generated roughly a 1" long and 0.5" wide damage size. Because of the wave dispersion, it is very difficult to interpret the difference in measurements in terms of damage size and damage location. However, by appropriately selecting a diagnostic wave as shown in Figure 6, the diagnostic wave form for the composite was preserved during transmission from the actuators to sensors before the impact. However, significant change in the wave form and phase was observed after the impact. The change of wave form and the delay of the phase were believed to be related to the size and the location of impact damage. With the selection of the diagnostic waves, the waves reflected from the boundary could be clearly detected, and, as a consequence, the possibility of the sensor signals being corrupted by the reflected waves could be minimized.

Currently, work is being conducted to develop an appropriate ASD technique based on propagating waves for detecting impact damage. It is believed that both the PSD and ASD techniques are essential for the development of a built-in damage diagnostic system.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A concept of built-in damage diagnostics for composite structures was discussed. The passive sensing diagnosis is good at providing information regarding the structural environ-

mental conditions. Together with the passive sensing diagnosis, the active sensing diagnosis is needed for detecting damage and monitoring the integrity of the structures.

Early studies have generated promising results for developing such a technology. However, besides the fact that the sensor/actuator techniques need to be continuously improved, considerable work is required to develop reliable and effective PSD and ASD techniques, which are the brain of the diagnostic system for in-service structures.

V. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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VI. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. Description of a proposed impact damage diagnostic system.

Figure 2. Comparison of impact force history between the predicted and the actual one.

Figure 3. The simulated sensor outputs corrupted by random white noise.

Figure 4. Comparison between the actual and predicted delamination size and length of composite beams.

Figure 5. Comparison of sensor measurements responding to a pulse wave generated by piezo-electrics for a composite plate before and after an impact.

Figure 6. Comparison of sensor measurements to a controlled diagnostic wave generated by piezoelectrics for a composite plate before and after an impact.

